

D-1.5. Recommendations and target zones for improved “One Health” surveillance.

Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics (ARDIG): The influence of geographic origin and management systems on resistance gene flows within humans, animals and the environment.

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The final goal of ARDIG WP1 is to provide recommendations for improved “One Health” surveillance at the European level.

Main conclusions and recommendations

On AMR

Collection systems on AMR often adopt specific standards and their corresponding evaluation criteria that do not cover all drug and bug combinations. Therefore, different standards and/or evaluation criteria are sometimes used for different drug and bug combinations in the same system. These systems show a lack of harmonisation within and between countries across the human and animal sectors.

Data collecting systems on AMR should collect data:

- applying the same standard (e.g. EUCAST or CLSI).
- using the same evaluation criteria (i.e. epidemiological cut offs or clinical breakpoints (or both in parallel))
- from both isolate types (i.e. clinical and non-clinical isolates)
- using a similar antimicrobial panel
- on isolates from the same sample type
- originating for the same animal categories

These requirements in the same isolate type should be complied in order to compare, evaluate and analyse AMR. Otherwise, data in most cases could not be directly compared.

The NRI approach is a statistical method that can be applied to overcome the lack of harmonisation on laboratory methods and methodologies. This statistical method requires quantitative data across a substantial range of values for the interpretation of data. Therefore, reports on AMR should provide quantitative values rather than data on the SIR level. Differences in results between automated AST methods and the micro broth dilution have been reported. Some automated systems have shown to be more accurate than other (e.g. VITEK 2). Therefore, in case an automated method is used, the specific method should be reported.

Significant dissimilarities were found between data on clinical and non-clinical isolates within animal categories and countries. Higher resistance proportions were mainly encountered in non-clinical isolates of broilers and turkeys and in clinical isolates of calves. This underlines that AMR data on clinical and non-clinical isolates need to be evaluated separately and preferably, both should be collected.

The lack of AMR harmonisation on further issues such as the lack of harmonisation on antimicrobial panels and animal categories remains. It is necessary to define a harmonised antimicrobial panel in clinical isolates and between clinical and non-clinical isolates.

Our analyses were applied in *E. coli* isolates of livestock between 2014 and 2017. However, this work could be extended in the future to other bacteria and for longer periods.

On AMU

On the medical side, it is significantly important to understand the data collection of the health care systems implemented in each country since the data collection procedure may vary. Therefore, data comparisons should be done with care. EU agreed units are not always provided in reports that show data from regional and national monitoring and surveillance systems on antimicrobial consumption in Europe. These units should always be applied.

ESVAC collects sales data from livestock in Europe using the agreed unit mg/PCU. However, this measurement only provides a general overview. Farm-level data are required for further analyses. However, there is no agreed unit for AMU in the animal sector. To overcome this issue reusing the already collected data, two different approaches have been suggested:

1. A harmonised unit for AMU
2. Numerator/denominator data to transform one unit into another:
 - a. The name of the active ingredient
 - b. The amount of active ingredient
 - c. The number of treated animals
 - d. The population at risk
 - e. The weight of treated animals
 - f. The time under treatment
 - g. The duration of the therapeutic effect of the active ingredient in the body

The implementation of the Reg (EU) No. 6/2019 on veterinary medicinal products will greatly improve the comparability of AMU data in a large number of animal categories.

AMU data collection should be provided by drug, animal species (e.g. broilers and turkeys instead of poultry), type of production (e.g. broiler or laying hens instead of chicken), age categories when the animal production cycle is long (e.g. weaning or fattening pigs instead of pigs) and the mixture of age category and production (e.g. calves instead of cattle).

Reports on AMU should always report on the same drug and antimicrobial drug categories for the same animal category that should likewise be defined in a harmonised way.

On AMU and AMR

Availability of harmonised usage data for animals will allow enhancing the analyses on the association of use and resistance across countries.

In the field of AMR in non-clinical isolates, EFSA drove the harmonisation of EU data-collection. However, there is no incentive to harmonise AMU and AMR systems on clinical isolates. In the absence of EU reporting, there is no requirement to harmonise. A large number of AMU and AMR collecting systems were found per country and sector. Some overlap between monitoring and surveillance systems on AMU and AMR was encountered. This overlap may be convenient for system and data validation. However, a better use of the available sources could save resources.

Overlap between reports has been encountered as a logical consequence of the presence of overlap between systems. AMU and AMR reports are published in different languages and time ranges. They should be provided annually in one international language to ease published data access.

Antimicrobial use was identified as an influencing factor on AMR. However, AMR prevalence might not necessarily decrease to some drugs if only the reduction of AMU is addressed, due to phenomena such as co-resistance and multidrug resistance. The AMR crisis must be addressed from all available angles (e.g. hygienic measures, vaccination, support of scientific studies and reduction of AMU) and as a collaborative action between countries.